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STUDYING THE INFLUENCE OF QUERCETIN FLAVONOID ON CONTRACTILITY ACTIVITY OF RAT AORTIC SMOOTH MUSCLE CELLS

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Abstract

In this work, the vasorelaxant effect of the quercetine in isometric conditions on the smooth muscles of the rat aortic blood vessel has been studied. In experiments, it was obtained that the vasorelaxant effect of quercetine depends on its concentration and with blockade of Ca_L^{2+} - channels in the plasma membrane of smooth muscle cells of blood vessels.

Keywords: smooth muscle, aorta, sarcoplasmic reticulum, phenylephrine, Ca^{2+} channel, quercetin, caffeine.

Introduction. It is known that pathologies of the cardiovascular system, including hypertension, myocardial infarction, stroke, occur directly as a result of disruption of the functional activity of ion transport systems of smooth muscle cells in the vascular wall [1, 2, 3]. The normal function of blood vessels is ensured by the activity of various ion transport systems located in the membrane of vascular smooth muscle cells and the sarcoplasmic reticulum [4]. It is noted that the voltage-dependent Ca^{2+} -channels located in the plasmalemma play an important role, and Ca^{2+} -transport systems are one of the central components in the implementation of the contractile function in smooth muscle cells [5].

In this regard, the study of the mechanisms of action of various biologically active substances on the ion transport systems of vascular smooth muscle cells can directly lead to the solution of the above-mentioned problem. Also, the study of biologically active substances isolated from plant species, the mechanisms of action of vascular smooth muscle ion transport systems is one of the promising directions in the creation of a new generation of pharmacological drugs with direct relaxant effects.

Up to date, a number of scientific studies have been provided to study the antiarrhythmic properties of many biological active substances such as alkaloids, diterpenes and flavonoids of plants origin [6]. However, the high demand for antiarrhythmic drugs for cardiotropic drugs and the ineffectiveness of the cardiotropic effect of diterpene alkaloids, i.e. the increase in

their negative inotropic effect with increasing antiarrhythmic properties, require further research in this area. Therefore, the study and search for biological active compounds with antiarrhythmic, antiischemic and antihypertension properties with low negative effect is of great practical importance [7].

In view of this, flavonoids are proved to be prominent plant-derived compounds generally found in fruit- and vegetable- rich diets with free radicals quenching ability. Quercetin, a member of flavonoids subclass – flavonols, has gained major attention due to its overwhelming potential. Quercetin was demonstrated to preserve diverse degenerative diseases by inhibiting lipid peroxidation [8].

Elucidation of the mechanisms of modulation of Ca^{2+} homeostasis in smooth muscle cells remains one of the most crucial problems of modern biophysics, biology and medicine. This is explained by the fact that the maintenance of Ca^{2+} homeostasis is of key importance for ensuring the functional activity of the cardiac and smooth muscles, and its damage are the main cause of the pathogenesis of various diseases of the cardiovascular system. Due to this, studies of the mechanisms of regulation of Ca^{2+} homeostasis in smooth muscle cells (SMCs) are not only of great theoretical, but also of great practical importance [9].

Materials and methods. Objective study of the effect of the flavonoid quercetin isolated from *Inula caspica* plants, on contractile activity of SMC in rat aorta.

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of the flavonoid quercetin.

Research methods and materials. In the experiments we used, isolated preparations of the aorta of outbred rats (200-250 g). The rats were decapitated by cervical dislocation, the chest was opened, the aorta was taken out and placed in Krebs saline solution of the following composition (mM): NaCl-120.4; KCl-5; NaHCO₃-15.5; NaH₂PO₄-1.2; MgCl₂-1.2; CaCl₂-2.5; C₆H₁₂O₆-11.5; pH 7.4. The aorta was cleaned of adipose and connective tissue and cut into segments in the form of rings 3-4 mm. The prepared segment of the aorta was placed in a special experimental chamber with a volume of 5 ml, where it was fixed with a silver wire between the rod of an electromechanical transducer (FT.03, Grass, USA) and the base of the chamber. The experimental chamber was perfused with oxygenated carbogen (95%O₂, 5% CO₂) and Krebs solution at a constant temperature of 37°C. Before the experiment, the aortic segments were preliminarily stretched with a load 1 gr and rinsed with saline for 60 minutes to achieve balance. Contractions of aortic preparations were induced by introducing phenylephrine (PE 1 µM) into the experimental chamber or hyperpotassic solution (KCl, 50 mM). Calcium-free solutions were also used in the experiments, for which Ca²⁺ ions were excluded from the Krebs solution, and EGTA was added to bind their traces (1 mM). The contractile activity of aortic preparations was recorded using a PIIT amplifier (Grass, USA) and an Endim 621.02 recorder (Germany).

Statistical data processing was carried out using the OriginPro 6.8 program (OriginLab Corporation; USA). In this case, the contraction amplitude was expressed as % of the maximum contraction (taken as 100%) induced by phenylephrine or hyperpotassic solution and was calculated as the arithmetic mean value for 4-5 different experiments. The statistical significance of differences between control and experimental values was determined for the data series using a paired

t-test. P values <0.05 indicate statistically significant differences.

Results and its discussion.

Previously, we found that the flavonoid quercetin effectively relaxes preparations of rat aorta preliminarily reduced with hyperpotassium (KCl, 50 mM) Krebs solution, which indicated that it suppresses the entry of Ca²⁺ ions into smooth muscle cells (SMC) through potential-dependent Ca²⁺ channels [10]. However, along with potential-dependent Ca²⁺ channels and Ca²⁺-transporting systems of the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR) also play an important role in ensuring the process of smooth muscle contraction [11,12]. Accordingly, the purpose of this work was to study the effect of quercetin on contractions of aortic preparations induced by the selective α-adrenoreceptor agonist and phenylephrine (PE), which basically provided Ca²⁺ entering through receptor-gated Ca²⁺ channels and Ca²⁺ ions released from SR [13,14]. In these experiments, to exclude the entry of ions Ca²⁺ in SMC through potential-dependent Ca²⁺ channels, the Krebs solution contained the blocker of these channels, verapamil (0.01 µM). In these conditions PE (1 µM) caused aortic contractions, the strength of which was 9.7±3.5% is less than the force of contractions induced by it in the absence of verapamil. Addition of quercetin under these experimental conditions was accompanied by a significant and dose-dependent suppression of PE-induced aortic contractions. Where in, the maximum suppression of the strength of PE-induced aortic contractions by 69.8±4.1%, from the control, was observed with 80 µM quercetin (Fig.2). The IC₅₀ value of quercetin (the concentration at which it caused 50% of the maximum effect) was 37.1 µM. These results indicate that the relaxing effect of quercetin can be provided not only by blockade of potential-dependent, but also by blockade of receptor-dependent Ca²⁺ channels.

Fig.2. Influence of the flavonoid quercetin on rat aortic contractions induced by phenylephrine in the presence of verapamil. By axis y-axis contraction force aorta induced by 1 μ M PE taken as 100%. On the abscissa axis, the concentration of quercetin. Verapamil-0.01 μ M ($P < 0.05$; $n = 6$).

It is known that the leading role in the development of smooth muscle contractions induced by PE are leading by Ca^{2+} ions released from SR through a specialized Ca^{2+} channel associated with 1,4,5-inositol trisphosphate receptor (IP3R) ([15]McFadzean and Gibson, 2002; Jackson, 2000). IP3R activation, provided 1,4,5-inositol trisphosphate (IP3), which is produced from phosphoinositol 4,5-diphosphate phospholipase C activated at stimulation of the α -adrenergic receptor. Where in Ca^{2+} ions released from SR make the main contribution to the increase in the intracellular level of $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ ions in SMC and the initiation of smooth muscle contraction ([16]Taylor, 2017).

In order to elucidate the possible effect of quercetin the release of Ca^{2+} ions from the SR through IP3R,

we have studied its effect PE-induced aortic contractions in the absence of Ca^{2+} ions in the medium, which are provided mainly by Ca^{2+} ions released from the SR through IP3R (Tykocki et al., 2013). Under these experimental conditions, PE (1 μ M) caused aortic contractions, the force of which was $70 \pm 3\%$ from strength contractions induced by it in a normal Krebs solution. In these experiments quercetin, also suppressed PE-induced aortic contractions in a dose-dependent manner, with a maximum at its concentration of 80 μ M, when the force of aortic contractions decreased by $45.9 \pm 3.8\%$, out of control (Fig.3). Meaning the IC_{50} for quercetin obtained under these experimental conditions was 41.5 μ M.

Fig.3. Influence of the flavonoid quercetin on rat aortic contractions induced by phenylephrine in Ca^{2+} -free Krebs solutions. Y-axis contraction force aorta induced by $1 \mu\text{M}$ FE, taken as 100%. The abscissa shows the concentration of quercetin. ($P < 0.05$; $n = 5$).

The results of these experiments persuasively suggest that quercetin effectively suppresses aortic contractions induced by PE in Ca^{2+} -free Krebs solutions, which are provided mainly by Ca^{2+} ions released from SR through IP3R. For confirmation influence of quercetin on the release of Ca^{2+} ions from SR and effect on caffeine-induced aortic contractions were studied. Caffeine causes a transient contraction of smooth muscle due to an increase in the level $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ in SMC, which is provided as a result of ryanodine receptor activation (RyR) when stimulated Ca^{2+} -induced release of Ca^{2+} from SR [17,18]. At the same time, it was found that the amplitude of the caffeine-induced contraction of the SMC is a qualitative indicator of the amount of Ca^{2+} ions contained in the SR.

In these experiments that performed in normal Krebs solutions containing ions Ca^{2+} (2.5 mM), caffeine (10 mM) caused aortic contractions, the strength of which was $67.5 \pm 2.2\%$ from strength contractions induced by phenylephrine ($1 \mu\text{M}$). Experiments showed that, pre-incubation of aortic preparations with quercetin was accompanied by a dose-dependent suppression of caffeine-induced aortic contractions. At the same time, in the presence of $80 \mu\text{M}$ quercetin, the strength of caffeine-induced aortic contractions decreased to the maximum by $56.8 \pm 3.4\%$, from control (Fig.4). IC_{50} value for quercetin obtained from these results was $42.6 \mu\text{M}$.

Fig.4. Influence of flavonoid quercetin on rat aortic contractions induced by caffeine in normal Krebs solution containing ions Ca^{2+} . Y-axis contraction force aorta induced by $1 \mu\text{M}$ PE taken as 100%. The abscissa shows the concentration of quercetin. ($P < 0.05$; $n = 6$).

The results of these experiments indicate that quercetin effectively suppresses caffeine-induced aortic contractions, which are provided by ions Ca^{2+} released from SR. However, in an increase $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ in caffeine-induced SMC, along with Ca^{2+} ions released from SR, Ca^{2+} ions coming through the plasmalemma from the extracellular medium can also participate [17]. Due to this, in order to clarify the mechanism of action of quercetin on caffeine-induced contractions of the aorta, its effects were studied in the absence of Ca^{2+} ions in the incubation environment. Under these conditions,

caffeine caused aortic contractions, the force of which was $35 \pm 2.4\%$ of the force induced by it in the presence of ions Ca^{2+} . In these experiments, pre - incubation of aortic preparations with quercetin was also accompanied by a significant suppression of caffeine-induced aortic contractions. At the same time, in the presence of $15 \mu\text{M}$ quercetin, the strength of caffeine-induced aortic contractions decreased by $26.1 \pm 1.1\%$, from control (Fig.5). IC_{50} value for quercetin obtained in these experiments was $38.4 \mu\text{M}$.

Fig.5. Influence of flavonoid quercetin on rat aortic contractions induced by caffeine in ion-free Krebs solutions Ca^{2+} . By axis y-axis contraction force rat aorta induced by $1 \mu\text{M}$ PE taken as 100%. On the abscissa axis, the concentration of quercetin. ($P < 0.05$; $n = 4-5$).

From the results that we obtained in these experiments show that quercetin has a pronounced relaxant effect and effectively suppresses aortic contractions induced by phenylephrine and caffeine in the absence of Ca^{2+} ions in the incubation environment. Due to the fact that the contractions of the aorta recorded under these conditions are provided mainly by Ca^{2+} ions released from the SR, these results indicate that the observed effects of quercetin are due to inhibition of the function IP3R. This inhibition of IP3R function and reduction release of Ca^{2+} ions from SR may be accompanied by decreasing in the intracellular level of the $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ level in SMCs and suppression of their contractile activity.

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